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Emulsion cocktail which consists of aromatic solvent such as toluene or xylene and non-ionic surfactant, is capable of incorporating up to 40 % water [1]. At first, the self-made emulsion cocktail was used for these experiments, however, since ready made one was commercially available, InstaGel or Aquasol-2 were purchased for the routine work. In general, the counting efficiency and background count rate are governed by the property of photomultiplier tube, therefore, in the case of prototype counter, EMI 9635 QB quartz face tubes were selected because of their excellent low dark current characteristics. Of course, the more low level tritium sample as deep well or deep sea should be enriched electrolytically even using the low background liquid scintillation counter. It is concluded that for an inexperienced technician in the developing countries the procedure of the low level tritium-measurement should be easy and simple, therefore, it is best way to adopt the direct liquid scintillation counting without prior enrichment.

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A THERMOLUMINESCENCE DATING STUDY OF CERAMIC FROM ANA-ZAGA IN GOBUSTAN

S.Mammadov, A.Ahadova

AR ETN Radiasiya Problemləri İnstitutu

a.ahadova@irp.science.az

Ana-zaga is a site located on the upper terrace of Boyukhdash Mountain, situated about 60-70 meters west of the museum building of Gobustan reserve, between stones № 29-32. The site contains a hearth, and a soil sample was taken from this hearth to determine its age using the Thermoluminescence (TL) dating method. TL dating is based on the fact that minerals such as quartz and feldspar accumulate a radiation dose (palaeodose) in their crystal lattice from

omnipresent ionizing radiation, including cosmic radiation, surrounding sediment, and radiation from the sample itself. This palaeodose gets erased when the minerals are exposed to light, but it accumulates again when they are buried by sediment and protected from light.

To determine the age of the soil sample from Ana-zaga, TL dating was carried out using the Harshaw TLD 3500 Manual Reader to measure the TL characteristics of the sample. The radiation dose was measured in the laboratory, while the dose rates were determined directly at the site or by geochemical/physical methods. Annual dose calculated as $2.34 \mu\text{Gy} / \text{year}$. The palaeodose for the sample was calculated as $35.20 \pm 1.36 \mu\text{Gy}$.

Using the additive dose method, the age of the soil sample was calculated to be $\sim 15000 \pm 1300$ years. This study highlights the importance of considering all necessary parameters in a dating project, as the lack of context for a sample, such as when a site has been destroyed, can make it impossible to determine the external dose rate and calculate an accurate age.

In conclusion, the TL dating method was successfully used to determine the age of a soil sample taken from the hearth site in Ana-zaga. The study demonstrates the importance of careful consideration of all parameters when carrying out dating projects and highlights the potential of TL dating for the accurate determination of ages of archaeological and geological materials.

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